

Early-successional species show higher tolerance of drought than late-successional species across Europe

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HIGHLIGHTS

- Early-successional species showed higher drought tolerance than European beech.
- The growth of Scots pine and silver birch trees increased with increasing latitude.
- Temperature during vegetation period drove silver birch growth during drought.
- All species showed a rather fast recovery after drought events.

GRAPHICAL ABSTRACT

ARTICLE INFO

Editor: Manuel Esteban Lucas-Borja

Keywords:

Drought event
Drought tolerance
Ecological succession
Fast-growing species
Pioneer species
Tree-ring chronology

ABSTRACT

Climate change is exacerbating forest disturbances through more frequent and more intense droughts and fires, undermining their ability to recover from such disturbances. The response of fast-growing early-successional species to drought is poorly understood, despite their key role in ecological succession and their ability to enhance ecosystem resilience. Here, we compared the growth responses to drought events of three early-successional species (silver birch, black poplar, and Scots pine) with that of one late-successional species (European beech) across their natural distribution ranges in Europe. We used tree-ring widths of 6340 trees from 109 forest sites to establish species-specific tree-ring chronologies. We then used multiple linear regression to analyze which climatic or growth variables (pre-drought growth and growth during drought) best explained the tree responses to drought. Silver birch, Scots pine, and black poplar showed superior drought tolerance, with a slight, non-significant growth reduction under drought, whereas European beech showed a significant decrease in growth. The variables that influenced growth during and after the drought were species-specific. Annual precipitation and growth variables were key predictors of post-drought growth for Scots pine, black poplar, and European beech. Scots pine and silver birch grew better with increasing latitude, i.e., in Northern Europe than in

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<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.scitotenv.2024.176997>

Received 24 July 2024; Received in revised form 14 October 2024; Accepted 15 October 2024

Available online 18 October 2024

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Central Europe, while European beech and black poplar showed more growth at sites with high precipitation during the vegetation and dormant period, respectively. This study provides insights into the drought tolerance of early-successional species and highlights their ability to promote ecological succession and facilitate the transition to drought-resistant, late-successional forest ecosystems.

1. Introduction

Anthropogenic activities are causing an increase in atmospheric CO₂ concentration, global temperature, and climate variability, resulting in more frequent extreme climate events such as heat waves and droughts (IPCC, 2012, 2021). In Europe, a marked increase in the intensity of droughts has been observed since the beginning of the 21st century, whereas an increase in the frequency of droughts has been documented since 1980 (IPCC, 2018; Spinoni et al., 2015). The summer droughts of 2003, 2018, and 2022 were particularly severe, and such extreme droughts are expected to become more frequent in Europe with ongoing climate change (Choler, 2023; IPCC, 2021). It is projected that precipitation and soil water availability will decrease in Southern Europe and increase in northern regions (Cheval et al., 2017; Fuentes-Franco et al., 2023). For Central Europe, different climate models show contrasting predictions, which range from an increase to a decrease in precipitation and water availability, with regional and local variability (Gudmundsson and Seneviratne, 2016).

In particular, the so-called “hotter droughts” (Allen et al., 2015), along with associated disturbances (e.g., insect infestation and wildfires), have triggered a widespread forest dieback phenomenon that is affecting forest biomes globally (Allen et al., 2010; Ciais et al., 2005; IPCC, 2021; Seidl et al., 2017). Resilience refers to the ability of a forest to maintain its functions during a disturbance, while recovery involves both the rate and time it takes for trees to return to their pre-disturbance growth and functioning (Ingrisch and Bahn, 2018; Lloret et al., 2011). Tree mortality is often delayed and can occur months or years after a drought, depending on the drought severity, environmental conditions, species-specific resistance, and recovery (Beloiu, 2022; Bigler et al., 2006, 2007; Hartmann et al., 2022; McDowell et al., 2008; Vitasse et al., 2019) as well as the interaction between soil properties and atmospheric drought.

The increasing frequency and severity of disturbances poses a challenge to the resilience of forests. Coniferous forests dominated by Norway spruce are now severely affected by drought (Lévesque et al., 2014), windthrows, and subsequent bark beetle attacks in Central Europe (Hlásny et al., 2021; Stadelmann et al., 2014). Despite efforts to transition from coniferous to mixed forests, 46 % of European forests remain predominantly coniferous, while 37 % are deciduous and 17 % are mixed (Forest Europe, 2020). To enhance forest resilience, there is a need to transition from species vulnerable to drought and infestations, such as Norway spruce, to more drought-tolerant species, particularly in Central Europe. Early-successional species can help bridge the gap between disturbed forests and the establishment of more resilient, late-successional forests. Consequently, silvicultural approaches are being explored to prioritize the establishment and promotion of drought-tolerant native or non-native species (Fuchs et al., 2021; Kunz et al., 2018). While these species provide habitat for other species, economic value, and aid forest restoration (Brockerhoff et al., 2017; Krieger, 2001; Tallis and Kareiva, 2005), their drought tolerance requires further investigation (Sandoval-Martínez et al., 2023).

When forests recover after a severe disturbance, early-successional tree species with a high migration rate (Meier et al., 2012) are essential to initiate forest succession. Among the most common and widespread early-successional species are *Betula* spp., *Salix* spp., *Populus* spp., *Alnus* spp., and *Sorbus aucuparia* L. Fast-growing early-successional species, such as silver birch (*Betula pendula* Roth), black poplar (*Populus nigra* L.), and Scots pine (*Pinus sylvestris* L.), can initiate succession (Spínu et al., 2023; Vacek et al., 2021). These species have large

distribution ranges across Europe. Silver birch is a fast-growing tree with minimal soil requirements and a wide distribution range across which it produces merchantable hardwood. It is considered stress-resistant but has a limited tolerance of extended drought (Beck et al., 2016). Black poplar is a riparian early-successional species with high ecological value; it is crucial for the renaturation of river ecosystems, e.g., for soil stabilization and as a windbreak (San-Miguel-Ayanz et al., 2016). Despite its tolerance of high temperatures, little is known about its drought tolerance (Bakewell-Stone, 2023; San-Miguel-Ayanz et al., 2016). Scots pine is regarded as a frost- and drought-tolerant species (San-Miguel-Ayanz et al., 2016), but it is increasingly subject to drought-induced dieback, even if such occurrences have been regionally constrained or are linked to specific site conditions (Buras et al., 2018; Hunziker et al., 2022). For instance, drought events reduce the regeneration of Scots pines and increase mortality at low elevations (Bigler et al., 2006; Bose et al., 2022; Rigling et al., 2013).

Climatic and growth variables play a crucial role in the health of early- and late-successional tree species. For instance, sufficient moisture availability in summer and mild winter temperatures are critical for growth, particularly for late-successional species such as European beech (Bolte et al., 2007; Leuschner, 2020), which is sensitive to drought (Ellenberg and Leuschner, 2010; Vanoni et al., 2016a). Further, Scots pine growth correlates positively with summer temperatures and negatively with late-winter temperatures (Diers et al., 2024; Grace and Norton, 1990). Moreover, pre-drought growth can be a determining factor in a tree's response to drought conditions, although this interaction is complex and varies among species and even across a single species' distribution range (Gessler et al., 2018). Scots pine trees with a greater magnitude and variability in growth before a drought event tend to be more vulnerable during droughts (Bose et al., 2020). European beech, however, often exhibits abrupt growth declines before mortality under drought stress (Vanoni et al., 2016a).

In this study, we aimed to compare the impact of drought on the growth of three early-successional species (silver birch, black poplar, and Scots pine) with that of a late-successional species, European beech, across their natural distribution ranges in Europe. Further, we investigated the effects of climatic and growth variables across all species and elevations, as well as tree growth responses to subsequent drought events. We addressed two main research questions: (i) Which species are more tolerant of drought and can recover faster? (ii) What are the key climatic and growth variables that explain tree growth responses during and after a drought event at the species level? We hypothesized that early-successional species show higher drought tolerance and faster recovery than the late-successional species due to their ecological traits. Additionally, we expect that climatic factors will exert species-specific influences on drought responses and recovery. To answer the above questions, we analyzed tree-ring data in combination with high-spatial-resolution climatic data from across Europe.

2. Materials and methods

2.1. Study area and selection of sites

We selected 109 forest sites across the natural distribution ranges of the selected tree species in Europe, spanning from the southernmost site in Spain (40.16° N) to the northernmost site in Norway (69.92° N). The easternmost site has a longitude of 49.29° E (European part of Russia), and the westernmost site is located at 5.36° W (United Kingdom). The selection of sites was based on the natural distribution ranges of the

considered species and the available tree-ring datasets that had been compiled (see Section 2.2). The 109 forest sites are home to silver birch (13 sites), black poplar (16 sites), Scots pine (53 sites), and European beech (27 sites), which are distributed along a latitudinal gradient. Given the spatial resolution of 1 km of the climatic data (see Section 2.3), all the selected sites were separated by a horizontal distance of ≥ 1.42 km, to reduce spatial autocorrelation. We extracted the elevation of each site using a digital elevation model at 30-m spatial resolution (EEA, 2016) and, based on this, calculated the slope of the sites. We selected sites from 0 to 1000 m elevation to reduce the elevational gradient and emphasize the latitudinal gradient. The sites were distributed across Mediterranean, temperate, and boreal forests (Fig. 1).

2.2. Tree-ring data

For all 109 study sites, we compiled tree-ring data for the four species. Tree-ring data were obtained from two open databases, namely the International Tree-Ring Databank (ITRDB) (Grissino-Mayer and Fritts, 1997; Zhao et al., 2019), and GenTree (Martínez-Sancho et al., 2020; Opgenoorth et al., 2021). Additional data for European beech and Scots pine were provided by Petritan et al. (2015), Petritan et al. (2017), and Hereş et al. (2021). The selection criteria for the ITRDB and GenTree datasets often prioritize dominant or co-dominant tree species coming from natural and undisturbed populations.

We used data from 6340 trees: 324 silver birch, 950 European beech, 4646 Scots pine, and 420 black poplar trees. The total number of trees per site was between 9 and 314, with an average of 58 (Table A1, Appendix A). As the age and size of the trees differed between sites, we detrended the raw tree-ring width series to eliminate age-related and low-frequency trends (Cook and Kairiukstis, 1990) and transformed

them into dimensionless tree-ring-width indices (RWI). We performed the detrending using the default settings of the ‘detrend’ function in the *dplR* package (Bunn, 2008) in the statistical software R 4.4.0 (R Core Team, 2020). We then fitted splines with a 50 % frequency cut-off at 67 % of the length of each series (Büntgen et al., 2006), and we built chronologies using the ‘chron’ function from the *dplR* package. For further analyses, we used these tree-ring chronologies, which represent the aggregated tree rings from the tree level per tree species and site. The final chronologies for the four species studied were limited to the years 1980 to 2018 (with small variations among species), corresponding to the period of available climatic data at 1 km spatial resolution (Fig. 2).

2.3. Climatic data and drought indices

To quantify drought events and their severity, as well as the variables influencing tree growth during and after drought, we used climatic data from CHELSA (Climatologies at High resolution for the Earth’s Land Surface Areas) at 1 km spatial resolution (Karger et al., 2017, 2021). The climatic data were monthly rasters for temperature, precipitation, and climatic water balance (CWB, i.e., the difference between precipitation amount and potential evapotranspiration), which are available from February 1979 to 2018. We defined drought events and drought severity using the standardized precipitation evapotranspiration index (SPEI; Vicente-Serrano et al., 2010), which was derived from the CWB. The SPEI considers the balance between moisture supply (precipitation, P) and demand (potential evapotranspiration, PET), with a low supply-to-demand ratio indicating low soil moisture availability and increased drought conditions (Berg and Sheffield, 2018). The SPEI is a multiscale drought index, which means that it can be calculated on different time scales and still be compared across different temporal periods and

Fig. 1. The 109 sampling sites used for this study and the natural distribution ranges of the four tree species in Europe, according to de Vries et al. (2015). *Fagus sylvatica* – European beech, *Pinus sylvestris* – Scots pine, *Populus nigra* – black poplar, and *Betula pendula* – silver birch.

Fig. 2. Mean tree-ring-width index (RWI) chronologies for 1980 to 2018, based on the individual RWI values for the four studied tree species. The vertical dashed lines denote the five driest years as identified by the 12-month standardized precipitation evapotranspiration index (SPEI) for June for the studied period: 1992, 1996, 2003, 2006, and 2014. The 12-month SPEI for June had the strongest correlation with RWI (Table A2a and Fig. A1, Appendix A). Each graph shows two species for better visualization of the mean RWI chronologies. *Fagus sylvatica* – European beech, *Pinus sylvestris* – Scots pine, *Populus nigra* – black poplar, and *Betula pendula* – silver birch.

geographic locations (i.e., 12-month SPEI values can be compared across various locations or years). The SPEI considers changes in evaporation demand caused by fluctuations in temperature, which is an important factor characterizing droughts (Vicente-Serrano et al., 2010). SPEI values from -1 to 1 indicate normal conditions, values < -1 indicate dry

conditions, and values > 1 indicate moist conditions. We selected extreme droughts based on a threshold value of $\text{SPEI} \leq -1.5$.

For the SPEI calculation, we extracted the monthly CWB for each site from the CHELSA dataset. We calculated the site-specific SPEI at different time scales (1, 3, 6, 12, and 24 months) from January 1980 to

Fig. 3. The 12-month standardized precipitation evapotranspiration index (SPEI) for three locations from Northern to Southern Europe from 1980 to 2018 (monthly values). Blue shading indicates months with moist conditions, whereas red shading highlights months with dry conditions. The three locations correspond to northern Norway (nops11), central Germany (deps04), and central Spain (ESPO01).

December 2018 using the R package *SPEI* (Beguería and Vicente-Serrano, 2022). The 1-month SPEI values represent short-term drought conditions, the 3-month and 6-month values represent seasonal drought, the 12-month SPEI values capture annual drought, and the 24-month SPEI values represent long-term drought conditions. The SPEI series on different time scales (e.g., 3-month vs. 12-month) cannot be compared for a specific location, as the standard deviation (SD) increases with increasing SPEI time scale (Vicente-Serrano et al., 2010). To calculate the SPEI for different time scales, the CWB is accumulated over the desired periods. This accumulated CWB is then standardized by fitting it to a probability distribution, typically the log-logistic distribution, and transforming it to a standard normal distribution. Finally, the cumulative probability for each value is determined based on the fitted distribution, yielding the SPEI (Beguería et al., 2014).

To capture the relationship between RWI and different seasons, we calculated the CWB for spring (i.e., the mean value of March to May), summer (June to August), autumn (September to November), winter (previous December to current February), dormant period (previous October to current March), and the vegetation period (April to September). In addition, we checked the correlations between RWI and annual mean temperature (°C) and between RWI and annual precipitation (mm). Fig. 3 shows the monthly 12-month SPEI patterns at three locations in Northern, Central, and Southern Europe. Using a Pearson correlation test with pairwise complete observations from the R package *stats* (R Core Team, 2021), we assessed the correlation between SPEI over different scales and seasons with the detrended RWI chronologies based on the RWI values of individual trees (explained in Section 2.2).

The 12-month SPEI for June had the strongest correlation with RWI (Table A2a and Fig. A1, Appendix A). Based on the above calculations, we extracted the 12-month SPEI for June series ranging from 1980 to 2018 for each site. Starting from these series and the selected threshold (12-month SPEI for June ≤ -1.5), we identified and selected drought and non-drought-years (Table A3, Appendix A). We identified a total of 215 drought events across the 109 analyzed sites (Table A1, Appendix A). The average number of years between drought events across all sites is approximately 8.3 years. Fig. 3 shows an increase in dry periods in Central and Southern Europe after 2000, while Northern Europe experienced fewer dry periods.

2.4. Statistical analysis

2.4.1. Drought impact on tree species

We assessed the tree growth response to extreme drought events. Growth during drought was given by the detrended RWI in the year of a drought. Pre- and post-drought growth were given by the average of the detrended RWI of the three years before and after a drought, respectively (Bose et al., 2020). We statistically evaluated the difference between pre-drought, drought, and post-drought growth across species as follows. We first tested the normality of the data with the Shapiro–Wilk test ($p > 0.05$) and the homogeneity of variance with the Levene test ($p > 0.05$). While the pre-drought and post-drought growth were normally distributed, this was not the case for growth during drought ($p = 0.028$), and the assumption of homogeneity of variances required for analysis of variance (ANOVA) was not met ($p < 0.05$). The differences in RWI between species were not normally distributed. Hence, the assumptions of ANOVA were not met, and we therefore assessed the differences between pre-drought, drought, and post-drought growth across all the data and between species with the nonparametric Kruskal–Wallis test ('*kruskal.test*' function) from the *stats* package and the Dunn post-hoc test ('*dunnTest*' function) from the *FSA* package (Derek et al., 2022), both in R. We additionally used the Kruskal–Wallis test to compare tree growth across sites that experienced two drought events between 1980 and 2022, to determine if successive drought events (as identified in Table A3, Appendix A) lead to decreased tree growth during subsequent droughts. We carried out all data cleaning and analyses in R, and we generated the maps in ArcGIS Pro (ESRI, 2022). We used illustrations

that were freely available from the Freepik website (Freepik, 2004) for creating better visualizations.

2.4.2. Quantifying the drivers of tree growth during and after drought

We used multiple linear regression models to better understand the drivers of tree growth during drought and the recovery of growth post-drought. We considered the following explanatory variables: pre-drought growth (mean of years 1 to 3 before a drought event and each of these years separately), temperature and precipitation for the specific drought year (annual mean temperature and precipitation, as well as values for each season: spring [mean of March to May], summer [June to August], autumn [September to November], winter [previous December to current February], vegetation period [April to September], and dormant period [previous October to current March]), slope, and the 12-month SPEI for June. In addition, to gain deeper insight into the relationship between RWI and climatic variables, we calculated Pearson's correlations of RWI and SPEI at different time scales, as well as correlations of RWI and climatic variables (annual temperature, annual precipitation, and CWB) across the study sites for the entire study period (1980–2018). To assess the overall pattern of tree growth during and after drought, we pooled all species together and applied a multiple linear regression. Further, we split the data into low-elevation sites (<500 m, 175 sites) and mid-elevation sites (500–1000 m, 45 sites) to determine if different variables play a role at different elevations.

We checked the assumptions of the multiple linear regression models, such as linearity, independence of observations, no multicollinearity, and homoscedasticity. To avoid multicollinearity, we built several models with explanatory variables that were not correlated (Pearson correlation $< \pm 0.7$; (Dormann et al., 2013). We then used the variance inflation factor (VIF) to assess multicollinearity among the predictor variables in these regression models. VIF values < 5 generally indicate low multicollinearity, suggesting that the predictor variable does not have a strong linear relationship with other predictor variables. In our case, the VIF values were around one. We combined two approaches to create the multiple linear regression models: (i) stepwise selection of a preliminary model; we selected the model with the lowest Akaike information criterion (AIC) value using the *stepAIC* function from the R package *MASS* (Harrell, 2015; Venables and Ripley, 2002); (ii) refinement: we evaluated the preliminary model, considering theoretical justification, multicollinearity, and model diagnostics; and (iii) manual adjustment: we added variables to or removed variables from the linear regression model (in a separate model), based on theoretical knowledge and the diagnostic results. We chose this approach to avoid overfitting and to ensure the theoretical justification of the selected variables. In some cases, we retained certain variables in the model even if they were not statistically significant. We made such decisions because their inclusion resulted in a higher R^2 value of the model, indicating that they contributed to its overall explanatory power (Burnham and Anderson, 2004). Retaining these variables helped us to capture more of the variability in tree species growth during the drought and recovery periods, leading to a more comprehensive understanding of the factors influencing growth.

3. Results

3.1. Impact of drought on early- and late-successional tree species

Drought events had a significant influence on the growth of the late-successional species and a lesser influence on the early-successional species (Fig. 4a, b, c). Silver birch recovered in the second year only, while the other species resumed their typical growth within a year of the drought (Fig. 4a). Growth during drought was significantly lower compared to tree growth before and after drought across all species ($p = 4 \times 10^{-8}$, Fig. 4b). Black poplar and silver birch had reduced growth during drought without significant differences pre- or post-drought ($p > 0.05$, Fig. 4c), with Scots pine showing the smallest reduction and silver

Fig. 4. (a) Growth trajectories of the tree species in the years before (–1 to –3), during (0), and after (1 to 3) drought years. The dashed gray line represents the overall expected value based on the entire RWI (ring-width index) series. Tree growth during drought compared with that pre- and post-drought for (b) all species and (c) individual species. The dashed line refers to the expected RWI without drought. The letters above the boxplots (band c) indicate significant differences between the mean ranks of groups, calculated by Dunn's post hoc multiple comparisons test after a Kruskal-Wallis test. *Pinus sylvestris* – Scots pine, *Betula pendula* – silver birch, *Populus nigra* – black poplar, and *Fagus sylvatica* – European beech.

birch the greatest. We did not find evidence that successive drought events (drought years identified in Table A3, Appendix A) resulted in reduced growth during subsequent droughts, as tree growth did not differ significantly between the first, second, and third drought years (Fig. A2, Appendix A).

3.2. Predictors of tree species growth during drought

The relationship between RWI and climatic variables across all study sites from 1980 to 2018 showed that the drought index (SPEI) was most strongly correlated with RWI. Specifically, the 12-month SPEI for June showed the most sites with a significant correlation with RWI (Fig. A1, Table A2, Appendix A).

The species-specific models for tree growth during drought revealed that each species was influenced by different climatic or growth variables. European beech grew more during drought at sites with relatively high precipitation during the vegetation period (p -value: 1.4×10^{-3} ; Fig. 5a, Table 1, and Fig. B1, Appendix B). Scots pine grew more during drought at sites with lower annual temperatures and higher pre-drought growth rates (–1 = the year immediately before the drought; R^2 : 0.28, p -value: 2.01×10^{-8} ; Fig. 5b, Table 1). For instance, Scots pine in Northern Europe showed that trees grew more during the drought than those in Southern Europe (Fig. B1, Appendix B). Black poplar showed a smaller drought impact on growth when there was more precipitation during the dormant period, yet this effect was not significant (Fig. 5c and Table 1). Growth of silver birch during drought was best explained by temperatures during the vegetation period, with more growth during drought occurring at sites with lower temperatures during the vegetation period, i.e., mainly in Northern Europe (Fig. 5d and Fig. B1, Appendix B).

When assessing pooled species and different elevations, the main predictors of tree growth during drought were climatic variables, such as

annual temperature and precipitation of the vegetation period (Table B1, Appendix B). Sites with lower tree growth during drought had higher temperatures and less precipitation. However, the 12-month SPEI and annual temperature had a significant effect on tree growth during drought mainly at low elevations (<500 m; R^2 : 0.14, p -value: 3.4×10^{-6} ; Table B1, Appendix B), while precipitation during the vegetation period was significant at mid-elevations (500–1000 m; R^2 : 0.10, p -value: 0.03; Table B1, Appendix B).

3.3. Predictors of tree species post-drought growth

At the species level, post-drought growth of European beech and black poplar were negatively correlated with pre-drought growth (1st year) (Table 2). Growth during drought, along with annual precipitation, explained 25 % of the variability observed in the post-drought growth of Scots pine (R^2 : 0.25, p -value: 1.15×10^{-7} ; Table 2), with more growth in Northern Europe than in Central Europe (Fig. B2b, Appendix B). In contrast, post-drought growth of black poplar was greater in areas with high annual precipitation, which mostly corresponded to the regions around the Alps (p -value: 0.02; Table 2 and Fig. B2, Appendix B). Silver birch post-drought growth did not show a significant pattern with the analyzed variables.

When examining pooled species and differences across low- and mid-elevations, the main drivers of post-drought growth were precipitation during the dormant period and tree growth during drought, along with additional species-specific characteristics (R^2 : 0.09, p -value: 0.0007; Table B2, Appendix B). Fig. B2a, b, c, d, Appendix B, depicts the spatial drought-related tree growth trends across Europe. At low elevations (<500 m), precipitation during the dormant period was the major driver (p -value: 0.007), whereas at mid-elevations (500–1000 m), growth during drought was the key driver (p -value: 0.003, Table B2, Appendix

Fig. 5. The most important variables explaining growth during drought, based on tree-ring chronologies (RWI, ring-width index) for the four studied tree species: (a) *Fagus sylvatica*, (b) *Pinus sylvestris*, (c) *Populus nigra*, and (d) *Betula pendula*. Each plot shows the partial regression line, with the 95 % confidence interval shaded in gray. The data points represent the observed values, with the regression line indicating the partial effect of each predictor while holding other variables constant. Table 1 shows the entire model based on multiple linear regression. *Fagus sylvatica* – European beech, *Pinus sylvestris* – Scots pine, *Populus nigra* – black poplar, and *Betula pendula* – silver birch.

B).

4. Discussion

We combined tree-ring chronologies and climatic variables to assess drought tolerance in early-successional species (silver birch, black poplar, and Scots pine) compared to the late-successional European beech across their natural distribution ranges. Our results show that early-successional species were more drought-tolerant than the late-successional European beech, with non-significant declines in growth, and key growth predictors varying by species. In addition, we found that climatic variables, such as precipitation, temperature (specific to a certain period), and pre-drought growth (1st year) were the most important predictors of tree growth during drought, whereas annual precipitation and tree growth patterns were the best predictors of post-drought growth. However, the drivers of tree growth during drought were rather species-specific and will be discussed in the following sections.

4.1. Impact of drought on the growth of early- and late-successional tree species

This study provides the first comparative empirical evidence of the growth responses to drought of early-successional (i.e., silver birch, black poplar, and Scots pine) and late-successional tree species (i.e., European beech) across their natural European distribution ranges based on tree-ring analysis. Silver birch was one of the drought-tolerant early-successional species, despite its slight growth decrease during drought and its prolonged recovery time (i.e., 2 years; Fig. 4a).

Similarly, another study showed that Japanese birch (*Betula platyphylla* var. *japonica*) showed high drought tolerance (Ranney et al., 1991). In contrast, Beloiu et al. (2020) found that silver birch saplings experienced considerable defoliation during the 2018 summer drought in Central Europe but that they recovered well in the subsequent years and only showed reduced vitality in 2021 (Beloiu Schwenke et al., 2023). In our study, mature silver birch trees showed a steady increase in growth over the three years after drought. The high drought tolerance of silver birch makes it suitable to withstand future droughts and support the transition from disturbed forests and the establishment of other species (Kunster et al., 2004).

Black poplar showed high drought tolerance in our study, with just a slight, non-significant decline in growth during drought, similar to silver birch. The evaluated variables did not explain black poplar growth during the drought, suggesting that subsequent studies should include pedological variables, including groundwater access, as this species appears to grow better on specific soil types, textures, and pH (Bakewell-Stone, 2023).

In the present study, Scots pine had the smallest growth decline during drought over its European distribution range (Fig. 4a). However, in other studies, this species showed regional vulnerability to drought, particularly at low- or mid-elevation sites (Bigler et al., 2006; Bose et al., 2022; Etzold et al., 2019; Hunziker et al., 2022; Rigling et al., 2013) or at the forest edge (Buras et al., 2018). The vulnerability might be driven by severe droughts, which Scots pine experienced locally (Bose et al., 2020). Similarly, Lévesque et al. (2014) found that severe droughts had little impact on the growth of Scots pine at a few sites. Therefore, Scots pine can still be considered a relatively drought-tolerant species throughout its range, although severe and prolonged droughts could

Table 1

Results of the multiple linear regression of variables influencing tree growth during drought: estimate, standard error, adjusted R^2 (in italic), p -value, and significance (** $p < 0.001$; * $p < 0.01$; * $p < 0.05$). The p -value is given for the intercept, for each variable (i.e., the p -value for each t -test), and for the overall model (i.e., F test, in italic). *Fagus sylvatica* – European beech, *Pinus sylvestris* – Scots pine, *Populus nigra* – black poplar, and *Betula pendula* – silver birch.

	Estimate \pm Standard error	P -value
I. <i>Fagus sylvatica</i>		
Intercept	0.47 \pm 0.22	$4.32 \times 10^{-13}***$
Precipitation vegetation period (mm)	$4 \times 10^{-4} \pm 1 \times 10^{-4}$	$1 \times 10^{-3} **$
Pre-drought growth (1st year)	-0.15 ± 0.12	0.21
Annual temperature ($^{\circ}$ C)	-0.03 ± 0.01	0.07
Adjusted R^2	<i>0.20</i>	$4 \times 10^{-3}***$
II. <i>Pinus sylvestris</i>		
Intercept	0.49 \pm 0.10	$3.77 \times 10^{-6} ***$
Pre-drought growth (1st year)	0.50 \pm 0.09	$1.09 \times 10^{-6} ***$
Annual temperature ($^{\circ}$ C)	$-0.01 \pm 4 \times 10^{-3}$	$7 \times 10^{-4} ***$
Adjusted R^2	<i>0.28</i>	$2.01 \times 10^{-8} ***$
III. <i>Populus nigra</i>		
Intercept	0.77 \pm 0.09	$1.67 \times 10^{-8} ***$
Precipitation dormant period (mm)	$5 \times 10^{-4} \pm 3 \times 10^{-4}$	0.14
Adjusted R^2	<i>0.04</i>	<i>0.14</i>
IV. <i>Betula pendula</i>		
Intercept	1.18 \pm 0.26	$1 \times 10^{-4} ***$
Temperature vegetation period ($^{\circ}$ C)	-0.04 ± 0.01	$6 \times 10^{-3} **$
Pre-drought growth (1st year)	0.34 \pm 0.19	0.09
Adjusted R^2	<i>0.26</i>	<i>0.01*</i>

affect it regionally.

European beech was more severely affected by drought than the early-successional species, but it recovered within a year. It grew more during drought at sites with more precipitation during the vegetation period, highlighting its vulnerability to drought, as mentioned by Rubio-Cuadrado et al. (2018). Other studies have shown that European beech depends on moisture in summer and mild temperatures in winter (Bolte et al., 2007; Leuschner, 2020; Roibu et al., 2017). Our findings confirm the sensitivity of European beech to drought. While species competition is known to have no effect on resilience (Castagneri et al., 2022) or just for a few species (Charlet de Sauvage et al., 2023), species composition can increase resilience depending on the species mixed (Charlet de Sauvage et al., 2023; Pretzsch et al., 2013). However, this has yet to be explored in the context of early-successional species composition with other species.

The suitability of European beech has special importance because of the current transition from pure conifer stands to broadleaf mixed stands in many European forests (Gessler et al., 2006). While European beech showed a decline in growth during drought, its growth may also increase if there is sufficient precipitation and warmer conditions (Marchand et al., 2023). Rapid recovery requires a consistently high growth rate, which has a positive effect on both sustained wood production (Bottero

et al., 2021) and maintenance of the amount of carbon stored during tree growth (Anderegg et al., 2015).

If droughts become more frequent in the future, as expected (Dai, 2013; IPCC, 2021), some tree species may not be able to fully recover in terms of growth before being affected by new drought periods (Anderegg et al., 2015). In addition, Hari et al. (2020) point out that consecutive droughts and very frequent non-consecutive droughts are likely to affect tree growth and survival even more than single droughts, although this depends on tree physiology (Grams et al., 2021; Hesse et al., 2024). Serra-Maluquer et al. (2018) showed that the recovery of trees was impaired after the first drought event and decreased with subsequent drought events. Therefore, species with a long recovery time are not an option for forestry, as successive drought events can lead to an irreversible decline in growth and ultimately death (Vanoni et al., 2016a, 2016b). At the local level, it has been shown that multi-year drought leads to a persistent decline in Scots pine growth and increases the risk of mortality (Bigler et al., 2006). We tested whether drought frequency influenced tree growth during drought, and there was no significant growth pattern between successive drought events. This indicates that all species studied are tolerant of repeated droughts.

4.2. Predictors of species-specific growth during and after drought

All species recovered within one year of a drought event, except silver birch, which had a slower recovery compared to the other species (Fig. 4a). Anderegg et al. (2015) showed that long-term legacy effects of severe drought depend on the species and can persist for one to four years. Silver birch growth during the drought was greater at sites with lower temperatures during the vegetation period, i.e., in Northern Europe, and lower in Central Europe (Fig. B1, Appendix B). Although this species was slightly affected by drought in Central Europe, it managed to recover within two years. Our dataset covers the central to northern range of this species; further studies should focus on the southern range, which is predicted to be more affected by climate change (Dyderski et al., 2018).

The post-drought growth of black poplar was positively influenced by annual precipitation and negatively influenced by pre-drought (1st year) growth. Compared with silver birch, black poplar needs more water to grow (San-Miguel-Ayanz et al., 2016; Weisgerber, 2014). Growth two and three years before a drought event, as well as the mean pre-drought growth (e.g., the mean of the three years before drought), did not significantly influence tree growth during drought or explained less variability compared with pre-drought growth in the 1st year alone. Consequently, growth in the 1st year emerged as a key driver for some of the species studied. This could be because certain species were exposed to drought conditions in spring that were not captured by the 12-month SPEI for June (which includes the months from July of the previous year to June of the current year). While the 12-month SPEI for June showed the strongest correlation with RWI across Europe, future research should focus on assessing the impact of spring or early summer drought on RWI.

We found that Scots pine growth during drought was mainly influenced by annual temperatures and pre-drought growth (1st year), with higher growth observed at cooler sites and at sites with greater pre-drought growth. Scots pine growth is sensitive to temperature; for instance, ring width correlates negatively with summer (July to August) and late-winter (January to February) temperatures (Diers et al., 2024; Grace and Norton, 1990). Hence, also during drought, this species grows better in areas with lower temperatures, whereas its growth is impaired in areas with higher temperatures (Table B1a, Appendix B). Further, growth during drought had a positive and annual precipitation had a negative role in determining the recovery of Scots pine.

Beyond climate, soil moisture over time is crucial for the resilience and recovery of tree species (Yao et al., 2023). While precipitation is a key factor in determining soil water availability, this is also influenced by soil properties such as texture, depth, and water-holding capacity. For instance, European beech with its shallow root system, is highly

Table 2

Results of the multiple linear regression of variables influencing post-drought growth: estimate, standard error, adjusted R^2 (in italic), p-value, and significance (** $p < 0.001$; * $p < 0.01$; * $p < 0.05$). The p-value is given for the intercept, for each variable (i.e., the p-value for each t -test), and for the overall model (i.e., F test, in italic). *Fagus sylvatica* – European beech, *Pinus sylvestris* – Scots pine, *Populus nigra* – black poplar, and *Betula pendula* – silver birch. SPEI: standardized precipitation evapotranspiration index.

	Estimate \pm Standard error	P-value
I. <i>Fagus sylvatica</i>		
Intercept	1.41 \pm 0.17	1.32 $\times 10^{-10}$ ***
Pre-drought growth (1st year)	-0.23 \pm 0.08	5 $\times 10^{-3}$ **
12-month SPEI for June	0.13 \pm 0.07	0.09
Adjusted R^2	0.15	9 $\times 10^{-3}$ **
II. <i>Pinus sylvestris</i>		
Intercept	0.67 \pm 0.08	<2 $\times 10^{-16}$ ***
Growth during drought	0.31 \pm 0.06	6.63 $\times 10^{-7}$ ***
Annual precipitation (mm)	-1 $\times 10^{-4}$ \pm 3 $\times 10^{-5}$	2 $\times 10^{-3}$ **
Adjusted R^2	0.25	1.15 $\times 10^{-7}$ ***
III. <i>Populus nigra</i>		
Intercept	1.13 \pm 0.10	1.59 $\times 10^{-11}$ ***
Annual precipitation (mm)	2.15 \pm 9 $\times 10^{-5}$	0.02 *
Pre-drought growth (1st year)	-0.25 \pm 0.10	0.01 *
Adjusted R^2	0.27	0.005 **
IV. <i>Betula pendula</i>		
Intercept	1.37 \pm 0.19	3.51 $\times 10^{-7}$ ***
Slope	0.01 \pm 7 $\times 10^{-3}$	0.04 *
12-month SPEI for June	0.19 \pm 0.10	0.07
Annual temperature ($^{\circ}$ C)	-0.01 \pm 7 $\times 10^{-3}$	0.09
Adjusted R^2	0.17	0.06

sensitive to changes in soil moisture and performs best in deep, well-drained soils (Leuschner, 2020). In contrast, early-successional species generally have deeper, more adaptable root systems (Paz et al., 2015), than late successional species, which enhance their resilience to fluctuations in soil moisture. However, edaphic data were not available for this study. Therefore, future research should investigate the interaction between climate and edaphic conditions to better understand their combined effects on tree species growth during and after drought.

Drought-resistant early-successional tree species will become even more important in the future, as they can ensure ecological succession and thus support the occurrence of other species. Our results provide new insights into the drought tolerance of these species. Further research on ecological succession after forest disturbances, based on early-successional species, could build on these results. Even though our dataset covered locations throughout the natural distribution ranges of the species, it could be enhanced to better capture the responses of these species to drought near the southern edge of their ranges (Dyderski et al., 2018). To achieve this, the tree ring datasets would need to be extended and combined with remote sensing data such as Sentinel-2 or higher resolution data to cover larger areas (Beloiu et al., 2022; Jevšenak et al., 2024). As the frequency and intensity of droughts have increased in recent years, with Europe experiencing droughts in 2018, 2019, and 2022 (Beloiu Schwenke et al., 2023; Choler, 2023), it would be interesting to conduct further studies on how these tree species responded to the recent droughts. Although we compared early-successional species only with European beech, the observed differences in drought tolerance between early- and late-successional species might be applicable to other late-successional species as well, given their similar ecological characteristics, yet further research should test this assumption.

5. Conclusions

We assessed the growth sensitivity of three early-successional and one late-successional tree species to severe drought along a broad ecological gradient across their European distribution ranges. We showed that the growth of early-successional species (silver birch, black

poplar, and Scots pine) is less affected by drought than that of the late-successional species, European beech. The results highlight the potential for incorporating early-successional species into forest management strategies aimed at increasing drought resilience. Early-successional species can be a source of timber and provide other ecosystem services, such as soil stabilization, biodiversity support, and carbon sequestration, while the late-successional species are establishing and reach maturity. However, with projected increases in drought intensity and frequency, the long-term resilience of these species may be challenged. Our research contributes to the ongoing efforts to enhance the resilience of European forests in the face of drought and other disturbances. It also provides critical insights into adaptive forest management aimed at improving the drought tolerance of forests.

CRedit authorship contribution statement

Mirela Beloiu Schwenke: Writing – review & editing, Writing – original draft, Visualization, Methodology, Formal analysis, Data curation, Conceptualization. **Christof Bigler:** Writing – review & editing, Methodology. **Any Mary Petritan:** Writing – review & editing. **Ion Catalin Petritan:** Writing – review & editing, Methodology. **Gioele Madonna:** Writing – review & editing, Formal analysis, Data curation. **Verena C. Griess:** Writing – review & editing.

Funding

No external funding was granted for this research. MBS acknowledges support from SNSF-Sinergia grant number 216562 and SNSF grant number IZCOZO_213355. AMP acknowledges support from the project “OPTimising FORest management decisions for a low-carbon, climate resilient future in Europe (OptFor-EU)” funded by the European Union Horizon Europe program, under grant number 101060554.

Declaration of competing interest

The authors declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal relationships that could have appeared to influence

the work reported in this paper.

Acknowledgments

MBS would like to thank Dr. Roman Zweifel and Dr. Arun Bose from the Swiss Federal Institute for Forest, Snow and Landscape Research WSL for insightful discussions on tree growth and drought indices. We also thank Dr. Melissa Dawes for professional language editing.

Appendix A. Supplementary data

Supplementary data to this article can be found online at <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.scitotenv.2024.176997>.

Data availability

Data will be made available on request.

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